

DICHOTOMY OF SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT: PRACTICES AND CHALLENGES

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the extent of application of the solid waste management programs and practices implemented in the different barangays of Dumaguete City. The participants of the study were the barangay officials and ten (10) residents of the 30 barangays. The statistical tools used in this study were weighted mean, Spearman rank correlation coefficient and Maan-Whitney U test. The study found the following: 1) among the identified six (6) solid waste management practices and programs, both the residents and the barangay officials had the same perception of the extent of implementing Creation of Barangay Solid Waste Management Committee which is high; 2) the problems encountered in the implementation of the solid waste management programs and practices were said to be serious particularly the lack of garbage truck and personnel to collect the garbage; 3) the residents had a passive level of participation both in the formulation and implementation of the SWM practices and programs; 4) the problems encountered by the barangays had a weak significant relationship with the extent of application of the SWM practices and programs; 5) a significant yet weak relationship was found between the problems encountered in maintaining the disposal of solid waste and the level of community involvement in the formulation and implementation SWM practices and programs; 6) there was a significant difference in the application of solid waste management practices and programs between the barangay officials and the residents; and 7) the belief of barangay officials was higher than that of the residents in terms of the creation of the barangay solid waste committee as a solution to solid waste disposal.

Keywords: *Extent of Application of Solid Waste Management Practices , Problems Encountered, Community Involvement*

INTRODUCTION

Problems on solid waste management remain a major environmental concern in many parts of the world today. They require immediate solution as they entail various detrimental consequences to humanity both in rural and urban areas. Solid wastes are generated by humans through the consumption of materials and industry products.

Consequently, consumerism has a big impact on the increasing volume of solid wastes. Cities worldwide produce 2.01 billion tons of solid wastes, which are translated into 0.74 kilograms for every person in a day. This would mean that the higher the purchasing power of an individual is, the higher is his/her consumption and eventually production of solid wastes (World Bank, 2023).

Solid waste management is the supervised handling of waste materials from generation at the source through the recovery processes to disposal (OECD Glossary, 2017). It is the field concerned with managing the generation, storage, collection, transportation, processing, and disposal of solid waste materials. This management can be effectively approached through various public health, conservation, economic, aesthetic, engineering, and environmental considerations (Leblanc, 2018).

Dumaguete City, a third class City in the Province of Negros Oriental, has been facing garbage disposal problems. In fact, the city generates eighty (80) tons of garbage each day. Due to the prohibition of the open dumps established and operated, and any practice or disposal of solid waste by any person, the local government units have considered using exclusive sanitary landfills to address the overflowing garbage spills on the roads near the open dump site in Baranggay Candau-ay (Partlow, 2017).

According to Engr. Chilvier Patrimonio, head of the City Environment and Natural Resources, during an interview on April 2019, the Candau-ay dump site has already reached its carrying capacity of accommodating garbage. In fact, a closure order has already been released since 2006. Because the city has a small land area, there has been difficulty finding a land which can be used as a dumpsite. Also, even if the city has already acquired a lot, it still has to comply with the DENR requirements to seek an Environment Clearance Certificate and to come up with 10 year tenure plan which itemizes the plans and activities to be done in closing the Candau-ay dumpsite.

The city has been criticized for its non-enforcement of segregation at source as provided in the City Ordinance No. 115 or the Integrated Solid Waste Management of Dumaguete City that mandates the segregation of solid waste into biodegradable or decomposable, non-biodegradable or non-decomposable, and toxic and hazardous wastes. The ordinance came as a result of Republic Act 9003, an act providing for an ecological solid waste management program, which mandates segregation at source.

Moreover, the city ordinance deputized barangay enforcers to facilitate in the stronger implementation of the ordinance.

This study was able to identify the solid waste management practices adopted and implemented by the thirty (30) barangays in Dumaguete City. Moreover, it looked into the involvement of the residents in coming up with solid waste practices to help the local government mitigate the problem in garbage disposals. As a result of this undertaking, a strategic development plan aimed at sustaining the solid waste management practices was formulated.

Research Questions

This study identifies the solid waste management practices implemented by the various barangays in Dumaguete City. It aims to answer the following specific questions:

1. What is the extent of application of the following solid waste management practices in the barangays of Dumaguete, in terms of:
 - 1.1 creation of Barangay Solid Waste Management Committee;
 - 1.2 no segregation, no collection Policy;
 - 1.3 promotion of composting of biodegradable waste;
 - 1.4 establishment of material recovery facility;
 - 1.5 promotion of reduce, re-use and recycle; and
 - 1.6 collection and disposals of solid waste?
2. What is the extent of the challenges encountered in the barangays of Dumaguete City as perceived by the Barangay Officials and the residents?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used the correlational and comparative methods of research. It also utilized the quantitative method of research. The correlational design is used to determine the relationships among variables and to allow the prediction of future events from present knowledge (Walinga & Stangor, 2014). In this study, the relationship between the solid wastemanagement practices applied and the challenges encountered were measured. Meanwhile, the comparative research design intends to compare two groups inan attempt to draw a conclusion about them (Richardson, 2018). In this study, the perception of the barangay officials and the residents were beingcompared in relation to the solid waste management practices of the barangay.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in the thirty (30) barangays of Dumaguete City, Negros Oriental. Dumaguete is a component city in the Province of Negros Oriental. It

has a total population of 131, 377 based on the 2015 population census of the Philippine Statistics Office. The city is politically subdivided into 30 barangays (DRRMP, 2018).

Statistical Tools

The tools used by the researcher in analyzing the data were the Weighted mean and Spearman rank correlation coefficient. Weighted mean was used in getting the extent of: (a) application of the different solid waste management practices; (b) the challenges encountered in the disposal of the solid waste and (c) community involvement in the creation and implementation of the SWM practices.

The Spearman rank correlation coefficient. This was utilized to identify the degree of relationship between the challenges encountered in the disposal of solid waste and the level of community involvement in terms of program formulation and implementation.

Research Respondents

The respondents of this study were the barangay officials in Dumaguete City and the residents per barangay. The researcher took 10 samples from each community in the 30 barangays. However, out of nine (9) elected barangay officials, only six (6) randomly selected barangays officials took part in this study.

Research Instrument

A self-made questionnaire written in the English language and translated into Cebuano was used as the basic instrument in obtaining the data required for the study. The questionnaire was based on the reading materials obtained by the researcher from different sources and from interview with the CENRO head Engr. Chelvier Patrimonio. To elicit comments and ensure the validity of the questionnaire, the researcher had the instrument crosschecked by experts, the CENRO head (Engr. Patrimonio), and solid waste management professionals William A. Ablong and Marlon A. Tanilon.

Data Gathering Procedure and Analysis

The research adhered to the established protocol for data gathering. result of the survey. The researcher conceptualized and determined the title of her study based on the thrust of the university research and on the current public concern. A design hearing was then conducted wherein the researcher presented to the panel members the title and content of her study for approval. After which, the researcher composed and sent a letter to the ABC President, Punong Barangays and the Head of the City Environment and Natural Resources Office to request for permission to distribute survey questionnaires. Participants received a consent letter explaining the critical elements of the study and the expectations as participants of the study. A consent form was

attached to the letter, which the participants signed if they agreed to participate and understood their role in the research.

RESULTS

Table 1 *Extent of Solid Waste Management Practices applied in the Barangay in Terms of Creation of Barangay Solid Waste Management Committee*

Indicators	Brgy. Officials (n = 180)			Residents (n = 300)		
	w \bar{x}	VD	Extent of Application	w \bar{x}	VD	Extent of Application
1. The Punong Barangay leads the solid waste management committee.	4.46	Strongly Agree	Very High	3.92	Agree	High
2. Barangay officials, Personnel and the community are part of the solid waste management committee.	4.46	Strongly Agree	Very High	3.86	Agree	High
3. The barangay allocates budget for the activities and programs of the Barangay Solid Waste Management Committee.	4.11	Agree	High	3.56	Agree	High
4. The committee formulates and enforces Programs and solid waste management practices consistent with the City's solid waste management plan.	4.05	Agree	High	3.57	Agree	High
5. The committee meets regularly to discuss updates and monitoring of the programs implemented.	3.80	Agree	High	3.54	Agree	High
6. The committee has its working manuals and guidelines as basis on how it runs, and it functions.	3.69	Agree	High	3.45	Agree	High
7. The committee works with other barangay solid waste management committee for any joint programs on solid waste management.	3.49	Agree	High	3.42	Agree	High
8. The committee coordinates with the City Solid Waste Management Board for its plans and programs as well as for possible support or assistance.	4.06	Agree	High	3.63	Agree	High
9. The committee is responsible for the monitoring of the programs and solid waste management practices implemented and the strict implementation of the city plastic ordinance no. 231.	4.02	Agree	High	3.61	Agree	High
10. The committee organizes the community in the promotion of solid waste management activities of the barangay.	3.86	Agree	High	3.57	Agree	High

Composite	4.00	Agree	High	3.61	Agree	High
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Application			
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High/Fully Implemented			
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High/Implemented			
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately High/Moderately Implemented			
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low/Partially Implemented			
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low/Not Implemented			

Table 2 *Extent of Application of Solid Waste Management Practices in the Barangay in Terms of No Segregation, No Collection Policy*

Indicators	Brgy. Officials (n = 180)			Residents (n = 300)		
	w \bar{x}	VD	Extent of Application	w \bar{x}	VD	Extent of Application
1. Garbage is properly segregated according to kind of waste produced in the households.	3.64	Agree	High	3.51	Agree	High
2. Households are using bins/sacks or other containers to store their segregated waste temporarily.	3.67	Agree	High	3.55	Agree	High
3. Bins are properly labeled (e.g. bio & non bio-degradable, recyclable & residual waste, toxic or hazardous wastes) to properly throw garbage according to its nature.	3.36	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.36	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
4. Garbage are not collected when it was not properly segregated in bins/used-sack/drum or other appropriate containers.	3.41	Agree	High	3.37	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
5. Household place tags on their garbage sacks. No tags, no segregation, no collection.	3.43	Agree	High	3.32	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
6. From the bins, segregated garbage are placed in different used-sacks ready for collection and transfer to the barangay material recovery facility for further segregation by waste pickers and segregators.	3.29	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.40	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
7. Violators are fined for non-compliance of the policy.	3.37	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.36	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
8. Provision of recyclable bins to designated drop-off point area in the barangay.	3.43	Agree	Mod. High	3.37	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
9. Provision of communal garbage bins especially to area which are not accessible by the garbage truck.	3.36	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.42	Agree	High
10. Provision of easy-to-follow guidelines (e.g. flyers, leaflets and the like) on the policy of	3.76	Agree	High	3.47	Agree	High

waste segregation policy.

Composite 3.47 Agree High 3.41 Agree High

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Application
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High/Fully Implemented
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High/Implemented
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately High/Moderately Implemented
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low/Partially Implemented
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low/Not Implemented

Table 3 *Extent of Application of Solid Waste Management Practices in the Barangay in Terms of Promotion of Composting of Biodegradable Wastes*

Indicators	Brgy. Officials (n = 180)			Residents (n = 300)		
	w \bar{x}	VD	Extent of Application	w \bar{x}	VD	Extent of Application
1. Provision of common composting facility in the barangay.	3.41	Agree	High	3.30	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
2. Conduct training to the community on basic composting.	3.65	Agree	High	3.34	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
3. Easy-to-follow guidelines are provided to the community about composting at source.	3.58	Agree	High	3.40	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
4. Households have their own composting bins.	3.21	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.32	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
5. The barangay is adopting a specific method of composting like vermi-composting.	3.20	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.09	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
6. Construction and operation of composting facility at the barangay level.	3.27	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.16	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
7. The barangay has composting equipment (shredder, sifter) to process biodegradable wastes into useful products, such as organic fertilizer (vermicast/vermi-compost).	2.83	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.00	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
8. Financial and technical assistance are given to the barangay.	3.05	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.15	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
9. Availability of permanent composting land area.	3.12	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.11	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
10. Barangay officials, personnel, community and other stakeholders are actively cooperating and participating in this program.	3.91	Agree	High	3.42	Agree	High
Composite	3.32	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.23	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Application			

4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High/Fully Implemented
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High/Implemented
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately High/Moderately Implemented
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low/Partially Implemented
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low/Not Implemented

Table 4 *Extent of Solid Waste Management Practices applied in the Barangay in Terms of Establishing Material Recovery Facility (MRF) at the Barangay Level*

Indicators	Brgy. Officials (n = 180)			Residents (n = 300)		
	w \bar{x}	VD	Extent of Application	w \bar{x}	VD	Extent of Application
1. Functional material recovery facility is present and available in the barangay that works according to its purpose.	3.16	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.23	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
2. The space for the MRF is enough to cater to the solid waste of the barangay.	2.99	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.05	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
3. Provision of labor and materials for the operation of MRF.	3.01	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.10	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
4. Logistics assistance is provided by the local government for the collection of garbage.	3.29	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.24	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
5. Necessary trainings on MRF are conducted to barangay officials and staff.	3.29	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.10	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
6. Segregation activities are properly observed in the MRF.	3.15	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.29	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
7. MRF is regularly maintained and monitored.	2.96	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.10	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
8. Recyclable materials are collectively sold to junk shops and proceeds are used to fund the operation of the facility.	3.03	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.29	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
9. The MRF is equipped with equipment (e.g. shredder, mechanical sifter) necessary for its operation.	2.65	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.00	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
10. The barangay has its own garbage truck and collectors.	2.70	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.05	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
Composite	3.02	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.15	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Application			
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High/Fully Implemented			
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High/Implemented			
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately High/Moderately Implemented			
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low/Partially Implemented			
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low/Not Implemented			

Table 5 *Extent of Application of Solid Waste Management Practices in the Barangay in Terms of Promotion of Reduce, Re-Use and Recycle*

Indicators	Brgy. Officials (n = 180)			Residents (n = 300)		
	w \bar{x}	VD	Extent of Application	w \bar{x}	VD	Extent of Application
1. Households are using eco-bags when shopping or going to the grocery store.	3.38	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.33	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
2. The households do not use single-use plastics in buying food and other personal needs.	3.31	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.18	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
3. The barangay has a recycling facility where local residents develop new products out of waste.	2.91	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.16	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
4. Trainings are conducted to the community on how to re-use, reduce and recycle waste materials.	3.52	Agree	High	3.32	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
5. The barangay sold products made out of the wastes produced by the community.	2.87	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.07	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
6. Banderitas, parols and the like used during fiestas, christmas season and other similar occasions in the barangay are all made from recyclable materials.	3.00	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.15	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
7. The Barangay conducts house to house collection of recyclable materials and sold to junk shops.	3.09	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.13	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
8. Ordinances on the use of single-use plastics are strictly implemented and monitored.	3.23	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.22	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
9. Households utilize plastic containers, bottles and cans for other home use.	3.50	Agree	High	3.37	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
10. The barangay hall utilizes the other side of a used paper for printing internal communications.	3.84	Agree	High	3.31	Mod. Agree	Mod. High

Composite 3.26 Mod. Agree Mod. High 3.2 Mod. Agree Mod. High

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Application
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High/Fully Implemented
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High/Implemented
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately High/Moderately Implemented
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low/Partially Implemented
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low/Not Implemented

Table 6 *Extent of Application of Solid Waste Management Practices in the Barangay in Terms of Collection and Disposal of Solid Waste*

Indicators	Brgy. Officials (n = 180)			Residents (n = 300)		
	w \bar{x}	VD	Extent of Application	w \bar{x}	VD	Extent of Application
1. The barangay has its collection drop-off points of garbage for each street/road.	4.01	Agree	High	3.66	Agree	High
2. Garbage is properly disposed through a garbage truck.	3.94	Agree	High	3.57	Agree	High
3. Open-fire burning of garbage is strictly prohibited.	4.02	Agree	High	3.59	Agree	High
4. Disposal of garbage in lakes, rivers and seas are punishable.	4.02	Agree	High	3.60	Agree	High
5. Ordinances pertaining to proper garbage disposals are strictly enforced and implemented.	3.80	Agree	High	3.58	Agree	High
6. The barangay has its own garbage collection system.	3.48	Agree	High	3.45	Agree	High
7. Regular garbage schedule collection is observed.	4.01	Agree	High	3.70	Agree	High
8. Collected and Segregated garbage are properly handled.	3.64	Agree	High	3.45	Agree	High
9. Placing garbage in the drop-off points without proper segregation is not collected.	3.32	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.32	Mod. Agree	Mod. High
10. Collection fees are charged at a minimal amount to fund solid waste management	3.03	Mod. Agree	Mod. High	3.23	Mod. Agree	Mod. High

programs in the barangay.

Composite	3.73	Agree	High	3.51	Agree	High
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Application			
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High/Fully Implemented			
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High/Implemented			
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately High/Moderately Implemented			
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low/Partially Implemented			
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low/Not Implemented			

Table 7 *Extent of Problems Encountered in the Barangays as Perceived by the Barangay Officials and the Residents*

L e g e n d	Indicators	Brgy. Officials (n = 182)		Residents (n = 300)	
		w \bar{x}	Verbal Description	w \bar{x}	Verbal Description
1	Inconsistent pick-up schedule of garbage by the government garbage truck.	3.19	Moderately Serious	3.52	Serious
2	Lack of garbage truck units in the city	3.47	Serious	3.59	Serious
3	Shortage of the number of garbage collectors	3.43	Serious	3.51	Serious
4	No provision of public garbage bins.	3.34	Moderately Serious	3.73	Serious
5	Less community involvement in the program	3.42	Serious	3.60	Serious
6	Lack of financial support from the city government	3.21	Moderately Serious	3.57	Serious
7	Weak information and education campaign	3.15	Moderately Serious	3.57	Serious
8	Weak partnership of private sector, NGOs and the community	3.16	Moderately Serious	3.61	Serious
9	Lack of technical capability to implement the program among the barangay officials	3.27	Moderately Serious	3.62	Serious
10	Lack of input materials to implement the program	3.29	Moderately Serious	3.68	Serious
	Composite	3.29	Moderately Serious	3.60	Serious

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description
	4.21 – 5.00	Very Serious
	3.41 – 4.20	Serious
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Serious
	1.81 – 2.60	Less Serious
	1.00 – 1.80	Not a Problem

DISCUSSION

Extent of Solid Waste Management Practices applied in the Barangay in terms of the Creation of Barangay Solid Waste Management Committee

Table 1 revealed the extent of Solid Waste Management Practices applied in the barangay in terms of the Creation of Barangay Solid Waste Management Committee. Data indicate that the Barangay officials “strongly agreed” that the Punong Barangay leads the solid waste management committee, and that the barangay officials, personnel and the community are part of the solid waste management committee as verified by a weighted mean of both 4.46 respectively which is equivalent to “very high extent” of implementation. This means that the barangays were able to implement 81%-100% of the expected SWM practices. The “very high” extent of application as perceived by the barangay officials would only mean that they, being elected by the people, are really serious about the implementation of the SWM practices. In other words, the barangay officials really do their functions as leaders of the community.

According to conventional wisdom, the best managers always lead by example, which would only mean that the Punong Barangay as manager should be the one to do the first initiative and take the first step to practice solid waste management in the barangay. This would also imply that the Punong Barangays mean what they say by doing it. In other words, they walk the talk. In Teresa, Rizal, their Solid Wastes Management Program was the result of the vision, passion, dedication, and consistency on the part of the officials and the citizens. Indeed, the municipal mayor walked the talk by inspiring the municipal and barangay leaders to discharge their responsibilities under the SWMP. The success of Teresa’s solid waste management program shows how strong political will and leadership by example, coupled with a sound strategy backed by a competent technical team acting as the focal implementing arm, and supported by the local citizenry, civic groups and industry/business partners, can create positive changes in the attitudes, values, behavior and practices of its residents, and help turn a town around towards lasting social transformation ([lgisb.lga.gov.ph ›uploads › best_practice › Teresa_-_Best_Practice1](https://www.igisb.lga.gov.ph/uploads/best_practice/Teresa_-_Best_Practice1)). Furthermore, the very high result is in line with the mandate of Memorandum Circular 2018-112 issued on July 12, 2018 by the Department of Interior and Local Government with regard to the Organization and Reorganization of the Barangay Ecological Solid Waste Management Committee, in which the Punong Barangay sits as the chairperson of the committee and at the same time involving barangay kagawad, SK chairman and other stakeholders in the community (Department of Interior and Local Government).

Similarly, the residents “agreed” with the same indicators as signified by the weighted mean of 3.93 and 3.86 respectively, which is equivalent to “high” extent of implementation. This means that the barangay was able to implement 61%-80% of the SWM practices. The rest of the indicators in relation to budget allocation, committee formulation and enforcement of the programs, committee’s regular attendance to meetings, barangay joint programs, coordination with City Solid Waste Management Board, monitoring of programs and city plastic ordinance, and the promotion of SWM

activities to the barangays were perceived by both the barangay officials and the residents as high, which implies that 61%-80% of the program was implemented. The result would only suggest that the level of involvement and awareness of the residents in terms of their knowledge of the solid waste management programs in the barangay given their perception on the extent of implementation is only high. Information education campaign is a factor that makes the residents aware of the activities, programs and steps that were taken by the SWM committee of the barangay. In an evaluation of the solid waste management project in selected barangays of Cotabato City, the personnel of the barangay solid waste management committee are non-elected barangay officials, yet they play an important role as forces of technical and administrative knowledge in shaping the policy of the barangay. The committee members participated in the door-to-door awareness and messaging campaigns (Welz, 2010).

Extent of Solid Waste Management Practices applied in the Barangay in terms of the “No Segregation and No Collection Policy”

Table 2 shows the solid waste management practices applied in the barangay in terms of “No Segregation and No Collection Policy.” Data indicate that the barangay officials “agreed” with the indicators on the provision of easy-to-follow guidelines on the policy of waste segregation and, the households are using bins/sacks or other containers to store their segregated waste as specified by a higher weighted mean equivalent to 3.76 and 3.67 respectively. Data further suggest a high extent of application, which means that 61%-80% of the solid waste management practices of the barangay were implemented as perceived by the barangay officials.

The above perception of the barangay officials would only mean that the “no collection, no segregation policy” is implemented but not very highly or fully implemented. In an interview with the President of the Association of the Barangay Captains, Hon. Dionie Amores, the researcher found out that there were still households who failed to segregate their garbage. As observed, most of the residents who do this were those in the middle class level of economic status or the educated or professionals. This finding would emphasize the importance of information education campaign and public participation for people’s awareness of the impact of the policy. Barangay Rosario, Pasig City, in 2005 started its solid waste management program through a survey on what needs to be done to implement the “no segregation, no collection” policy before coming up with an ordinance. The barangay captain coordinated with the various sectors in the barangay when conducting the survey. An information campaign, which includes distribution of leaflets to households to teach them how to properly segregate was then launched (National Solid Waste Management Commission).

Meanwhile, the data further show that the residents “agreed” with the two indicators “the households are using bins/sacks or other containers to store their segregated waste temporarily,” and “proper waste segregation in the household” as revealed by the weighted means of 3.55 and 3.51 respectively, which means that the extent of application is “high”. This finding suggests that the residents are practicing

segregation of waste although their implementation is not very high. This is relatively explained in a study entitled “Sustainable Solid Waste Management System in Brgy. Bayog, Los Baños, Laguna” wherein waste segregation is practiced especially for recyclable materials and the residents are re-using it particularly the plastic bottles, bottles and paper, while only a few are re-using plastic bags and metal cans. As a result, plastics and metals are mixed with other solid wastes unsegregated. Also, although people who belong to class B would have separate garbage bins for biodegradable and non-biodegradable solid, these were being handled by their household helpers who might possibly mix the garbage in time of collection. Hence, educating the members of the households is important, too (Almazan et al., 2016).

The composite weighted mean for the Barangay Officials and the residents are 3.47 and 3.41 respectively, meaning both “agreed,” which implies that the extent of implementation of the “no segregation, no collection policy” is high. The composite result is supported by the study entitled “The Perception of the Effectiveness of the Implemented Policy: ‘No segregation, No collection policy’ Project of Celdran Village, Tubod, Iligan City” which found that the policy is effective although the levels of effectiveness vary or are not the same due to the population in the three areas where the study was observed. Moreover, despite the effectiveness of the area, still the policy was seen as flawed and was not followed by some (Legaspina et al.).

In addition, local governments blamed the lack of awareness and discipline of waste generators as the reasons for having poor segregation. Although in Quezon City and San Fernando City, micro experiences work especially in terms of targeted waste segregation and collection. Effective segregation at source and segregated collection result to high waste diversion which would mean that waste from disposal should go to recycling and composting facility as experienced by San Carlos City. The change in behavior of the citizens towards awareness of segregation at source and the 3R’s can be translated into efficient and segregated collection, recycling infrastructures and incentives (Atienza et al., 2011).

In relation to the Theory of Planned behavior, the high implementation result would explain that the residents and barangay officials’ behavior towards “no collection and no segregation policy” needs to be transformed through full observance and practice of strict segregation at source by all the residents in the community. In the study “Waste Segregation Behavior at Source: Attitude, Perceived Behavioral Control, Subjective Norm, and Environmental Education,” it was revealed that the overall factors that influenced household segregation behavior at source indicated that the respondents had a favorable behavior (Cheng et al. 2017).

Extent of Solid Waste Management Practices applied in the Barangay in the Promotion of Composting

Table 3 shows the extent of solid waste management practices applied in the barangay specifically in the promotion of composting of biodegradable wastes. Both the barangay officials and the residents “agreed” that the barangay officials, personnel, the

community and other stakeholders are actively participating in the promotion of composting of biodegradable wastes as indicated by the weighted means of 3.91 and 3.42 respectively, which is equivalent to “high” extent of implementation, meaning 61%-80% of the solid waste management program was implemented by the barangay. The result would show that the barangays are doing composting of biodegradable wastes. However, in doing so, there are challenges that hinder its full implementation.

During the interview, ABC President, Hon. Dionie Amores, strongly encouraged the rest of the Punong Barangays in Dumaguete City to really find ways to look for a lot where they could put-up a composting facility so that the biodegradable wastes segregated can be utilized as compost fertilizer, thereby lessening the garbage or waste thrown in an open dump site. In Motong, for instance, the barangay negotiated with a private land owner and asked if the barangay could use his land for the aforementioned purpose. After knowing the intention and impact of the project, the land owner openly allowed his lot to be utilized as a composting facility.

Another consideration that would somehow influence the composting practices is the social and political capital which plays a significant role in land acquisition and affects the running and sustainability of the activities when running a composting plant. Aside from that, development of less land intensive composting technologies is necessary. It is waste concern that compelled low in-come areas in Dhaka, Bangladesh to make a small barrel type composting projects. The individual and small groups of families are provided with a concrete or steel barrel where organic waste is placed and harvested as mature compost from the bottom after a period of four (4) months (Rouse, 2004).

The second highest weighted mean indicator for the composting of biodegradable as perceived by the Barangay Officials and residents is indicator number 2, “The conduct of training to the community on basic composting”, with a weighted mean of 3.65 and 3.34 respectively. The extent of application by the barangay officials (“highly”/implemented”) differs from that of the residents (“moderately high/moderately implemented”). These results would mean that in terms of basic know-hows on composting practices as a way of managing the solid waste, barangay officials believed to have it implemented. However, this was moderately agreed by the residents. Such result would simply mean that the conduct of training for the residents of the barangay in relation to composting is not fully observed. As a result, not all residents practice composting in their backyard.

In connection to this, according to a study “Perception of the selected Residents on Household Composting in a Highly Urbanized Area, Manila Philippines,” the residents were knowledgeable about the traditional composting where the biodegradable materials are buried in the soil. People think that this can only be done in rural areas since these places have more available lands as compared to an urban setting. Accordingly, there are controlled parameters that should be considered when conducting composting activity to achieve the optimal condition, and these factors include Carbon-to-Nitrogen ratio, shredding of materials, blending of materials,

temperature, reaction or pH level, moisture and aeration, and microorganisms involved. Once the best condition is not met, this affects the processing or it may not actually happen. One of the existing methods of composting, based on how the residents described their method, is pit composting or digging a hole where the organic wastes are to be buried (Atega et al, 2018).

For indicators 4 until 9, both the barangay officials and the residents moderately agreed with the application, which is equivalent to moderately high or moderate implementation. This finding is a result of peoples' attitude and the political will of the barangay officials. In a study on the Information Dissemination Culture in Naga City, it was revealed that despite the encouragement of the SolidWaste Management board on the use of composting and recycling, little has been achieved due to the lack of participation and lukewarm attitudes from the public (Nolasco, et al, 2019).

The moderately high extent of application could also be attributed to lack of knowledge on the technical aspects of composting like the equipment to use and the entire composting process. Another likely reason could be space constraints since urban residents have a small land area (Nsimbe et al., 2018).

The lack of support from the national government could also be the reason for the moderate extent of application on the part of the barangay officials. The lack of funding and equipment becomes one of the challenges identified in implementing an integrated solid waste management plan (Nlerum, n.d.).

Extent Of Solid Waste Management Practices Applied In The Barangay In Terms Of The Material Recovery Facility

Table 4 shows the extent of solid waste management practices applied in the barangay in terms of the Material Recovery Facility. For indicator "Necessary trainings on MRF are conducted to barangay officials and logistics assistance is provided by the local government for the collection of garbage," the barangay officials have a rating scale of 3.29, which means that the extent of application is "moderately high or moderately implemented" as perceived by the barangay officials. The need for training on operating MRF is indeed necessary. The lack of training would likely affect how the facility would function. Having personnel who lack training may result to difficulty in delivering the required output. This is supported by Elnaga et. al. (2013) who maintained that training plays a vital role in building the competencies of employees for them to perform effectively in their jobs. In putting up a material recovery facility, there are considerations in terms of parameters in the operation of the facility particularly waste generators, waste composition, waste generation, waste diversion and market requirements. Hence, knowing these things is necessary for a functional material recovery facility (Asian Development Bank).

The need for logistic assistance is also necessary especially in hauling those residual waste that can no longer be utilized in the material recovery facility. Due to lack of garbage trucks collection, disposal became a problem. In the interview, Hon. Amores

stated that they are already working and soon to implement the use of tri- bikes especially in collecting recyclable and compost wastes which shall have a minimal fee of P10.00, the proceeds of which shall be used for the maintenance of the facility and tri-bikes.

On the other hand, indicators “segregation activities are properly observed in the MRF and recyclable materials are collectively sold to junk shops and proceeds are used to fund the operation of the facility” both have a weighted mean of 3.29, which means the extent of application is “moderately high or moderately implemented” as perceived by the residents. The result reveals that only half are operating and doing the segregation in the facility where proceeds were sold to junk shops. As stated by Hon. Amores, Barangay Junob is the pioneer in terms of the establishment of material recovery facility which performs the traditional or manual operation. Furthermore, Head of CENRO Dumaguete Engr. Patrimonio said that not all barangays have the material recovery facility because of the availability of the land.

The barangay officials and the residents both “moderately agreed” with indicators 3, 4, 6, 7, 9 & 10. Hence, the extent of application is “moderately high or moderately implemented.” Both residents and barangay officials have the same perceptions of the extent of the application of material recovery facility based on the composite result on the extent of application. The result is strengthened by the data from observation and interview which suggest that most of the material recovery facilities of the barangays in Dumaguete City are situated in the public land and some barangays who do not have the facility because of their location.

RA 9003 mandates the establishment of a Materials Recovery Facility (MRF) in every barangay or cluster of barangays establish in a barangay-owned or -leased land determined by the barangay through its Sanggunian. The MRF shall receive mixed waste for final sorting, segregation, composting, and recycling while residual wastes shall be transferred to a long term sanitary landfill (LawPhil Project).

Despite of the mandate of RA 9003 that there should be an MRF, having MRF is not completely implemented due to some challenges. For example, the MRF in barangay Candau-ay is at present is not operational because of the area where it was installed. ABC President Hon. Amores admitted that installation of such facility in the barangay level is really difficult to attain because of some challenges in the financial aspect. Running an MRF requires logistics or transportation, equipment and most especially additional manpower. Furthermore, the establishment of material recovery facility in the different villages or community in the Philippines has been a challenge. Although this is required under the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2001, it has attained a limited degree of success, which is attributed to the lack of, or incomplete, understanding of the basic aspects of material recovery facilities in terms of design, construction, and operations, as well as the parameters for a successful and sustained operation (Asian Development Bank, 2013).

In San Fernando, Pampanga, there are a total of one hundred (100) MRFs. Besides, the 35 barangays, subdivisions and schools decided to build their own facility. The city devoted resources of P150, 000 for the construction of MRF and distribution of tri-bikes and push carts for the garbage collectors of the barangay (Ranada, 2015).

On the other hand, Barangay Bayog, Los Baños, Laguna” does not have a material recovery facility. Solid waste materials collected in the barangay are brought to the material recovery facility of barangay Timugan (Almazan, C, 2016). Likewise, barangays in Tacloban City lack material recovery facilities (Zero Waste Cities Asia Series).

Extent Of Solid Waste Management Practices In The Barangay In Terms Of Promotion Of Reduce, Re-Use, Recycle

Table 5 shows the extent of solid waste management practices applied in the barangay in terms of promotion of reduce, re-use, recycle. The Barangay officials “agreed” with indicator “utilizing the other side of a used paper for printing internal communications” as revealed by a weighted mean of 3.84, which means that the extent of application is “high”. This would imply that in order to maximize and utilize scratch paper, the barangay hall is implementing non-single use of paper. In this way, the barangay could save budget for stationery supplies. This initiative depicts implementers or enforcers as leading by example. People would most likely follow a leader or emulate the action if they see that the leader himself takes the lead in doing recycling initiatives.

Meanwhile, the residents “moderately agreed” with “the utilization of plastics containers, bottles and cans for other household use” as reflected in the weighted mean of 3.37, which suggests that the extent of application is “moderately high or moderately implemented.” This result would mean that only 50% of the respondents believe and act what is stated in the indicator. This strengthens the findings of Almazan et al. (2016) that the respondents of the study re-use plastic bottles, bottle, and paper, but very few re-use plastic bags and metal cans. For indicators numbers 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, and 8, both the barangay officials and the residents have similar perception of the extent of application, which is “moderately high or moderately implemented.” The result would only explain the behavior of the residents in terms of doing reduce, re-use and recycle. This means that their behavior towards the acts is still not strong. As observed, there are still barangays who use plastic banderitas when celebrating fiestas in their area.

The 3Rs gap in action and practices is due to the lack of education and awareness, including the lack of support and allocation of 3Rs facilities (Lim et al., 2017).

City ordinance no. 231 on “ No Plastic Everyday” bans the use of plastic bag in all business establishments including malls and supermarkets in the city of Dumaguete. This city ordinance helps in minimizing our solid wastes. In this policy, people will be forced to use containers or eco-bags whenever they shop. Hence, they could re-use their empty containers or bags for their purchase of goods, thereby practicing reduce

and re-use. Nevertheless, despite this city ordinance, the use of single use plastics is still existent in both supermarkets and public markets. In other words, there was no strict implementation of the ordinance. The political will to implement is so weak, which reflects Filipinos' ningas cogon mentality. That is why sustainability of the program is being questioned as not everyone is doing it.

According to Engr. Chelvier Patrimonio, in response to city ordinance "no plastic everyday," food chains and restaurants are now using biodegradable straws, and when buying food for take-out, people use recyclable plastics or paper packs instead of plastic food wraps. But then again, this remains a continuing struggle since not all are observing and practicing it.

The lack of recycling skills could be a significant barrier to recycling participation. Hence, people should be well educated how to recycle waste in practice. Moreover, the support systems and perceived recycling skills are crucial factors to be the key of people's decision to drive their recycling intention to the actual action (A. Ittiravivongs, 2011).

Extent Of Solid Waste Management Practices In The Barangay In Terms Of Collection and Disposal

Table 6 shows the solid waste management practices applied in the barangay in terms of the collection and disposal of solid waste. It is shown that the open-fire burning is strictly prohibited in the barangay and disposal of garbage in lakes, rivers and seas is punishable by law as indicated by the weighted mean of 4.02; therefore, the extent of application is "high" as perceived by the barangay officials.

The result would imply that the barangay officials are somehow enforcing penalties to violators in relation to disposal of solid waste. Still, in some rural areas in the Philippines, burning of yarn waste is still practiced in the barangay level despite the law prohibiting it (Abueva et al., 2016). As stipulated in RA 9003, open burning of solid waste as well as littering, throwing, dumping of waste matters in public places, such as roads, sidewalks, canals, esteros or parks, and establishment, or causing or permitting the same is prohibited. Violation of the law would mean penalty or fines of not less than Three hundred pesos (P300.00) but not more than One thousand pesos (P1,000.00) or imprisonment of not less than one (1) day but not more than fifteen (15) days, or both; and upon conviction, the violator shall be punished with a fine of not less than Three hundred pesos (P300.00) but not more than One thousand pesos (P1,000.00) or render community service for not less than one (1) day to not more than fifteen (15) days to an LGU where such prohibited acts are committed, or both, respectively (The Lawphil Project).

On the other hand, the residents in the barangay "agreed" with "regular schedule of collection of garbage is observed" as indicated by the weighted mean of 3.70. This implies that the extent of application is "high". In other words, the residents believed that the city is collecting garbage regularly. However, this contradicts the statement of the

CENRO Head of the city who claimed that the collection of garbage in the barangay has also been a challenge since the city only has five (5) garbage trucks that collect the garbage of the entire city and there are also days that the personnel in charge of collecting fail to go to work. Thus, it would take days to collect the garbage from other barangays. Hon. Amores emphasized that segregation at source would help maximize the use of garbage trucks since only the residual wastes are collected as they can no longer be used. Both the residents and barangay officials “agreed” with indicators 1, 2, 5, 6, and 8. Hence, the extent of application is “high.”

Both groups of respondents “moderately agreed” with indicators 9 and 10, which means that the extent of application as “moderately high/moderately implemented.” Overall, the composite weighted mean description is “agree” and the extent of application is “high” as perceived by both barangay officials and residents.

The result would reveal that both barangay officials and residents believed that the indicators are being done and implemented although it may not be a full implementation. For instance, in Barangay Bantayan where it currently has 5 waste collection vehicles and 7 wastes collectors working 3 times a week, the garbage from the households dropped by 20% and amazingly 92% of their biodegradable wastes also dropped because the residents are practicing composting (Pagunsan, 2019).

In Barangay Looc, a barangay ordinance was passed whereby enforcers, sweepers, and the so-called waste heroes or the collectors, are tasked to collect all types of garbage daily from more than 1,000 households with a fee of PHP30 a month (Gallarde, 2018).

Under the RA 9003, collection, transport and disposal of solid wastes are the responsibilities of the local government units (LGUs). Most local government units, at present, administer their own collection systems or contract this service out to private contractors. Like in the case in Metro Manila, the common types of collection vehicles are open dump trucks and compactor trucks. About 40 to 85 percent of solid wastes are generated nationwide while it is 85 percent in Metro Manila. The poorer areas of cities, municipalities, and rural barangays are typically unserved or under-served. As a result, the uncollected waste ends up mostly in rivers, esteros and other water bodies, thus, polluting major water bodies and clogging the drainage systems, which cause flooding during heavy rains. Accordingly, the 85 percent collection rate of Metro Manila is above the average collection rate of other cities in the Philippines (around 69%) and among East Asia and Pacific countries (around 72%). The general practice of solid waste disposal in the country remains open dumping as controlled dumpsites and sanitary landfills are very limited. However, the number of sanitary landfills is insufficient to serve all the LGUS (Senate of the Philippines, 2017).

Extent of the Challenges Encountered in The Implementation of The Solid Waste Management Practices in The Barangay

Table 7 shows the extent of the challenges encountered in the implementation of the solid waste management practices in the barangay. Based on the results, barangay officials perceived that the lack of garbage truck units in the city, shortage of the number of garbage collectors and the lack of community involvement are “serious” challenges as revealed by the weighted mean of 3.47, 3.43 and 3.42 respectively. This would imply that the lack of garbage trucks would put the health of the residents at risk due to exposure to the pungent smell of the garbage. This would also affect the efficiency of collection due to the lack of garbage trucks and shortage of garbage collectors. In Thailand, for instance, having inadequate waste collection vehicles was one of the barriers for effective municipal solid waste management. The waste collection trucks were always full before it reached the end of their routes (Yukalang et al., 2017). Past studies also reported that the low number of waste vehicles for collection negatively affects the collection, transfer and transport process of garbage (Sulemana et al., 2018).

The lack of garbage truck as a serious problem does not equate to indicator no. 3 in Table 6, which is “garbage is properly disposed through a garbage truck,” with high extent of implementation as perceived by both barangay officials and the residents. The latter illustrates only the means on how the garbage is brought to the designated dump site. Moreover, it talks about the system concerning how the garbage is handled and not disposed anywhere. It does not correlate with the number of units of the garbage trucks. The lack of garbage trucks is relatively linked to the efficiency of the collection or pick-up of the garbage.

Indicator “weak information and education campaign” was perceived by the barangay officials as a “moderately serious problem,” while it was perceived by the residents as a “serious problem.” Comparing it to the result presented in Table 5, indicator 4 “trainings are conducted to the community on how to reduce, re-use and recycle” was perceived by the barangay officials as highly implemented, while it was perceived by the residents as moderately implemented. The weak information and education campaign was perceived by the residents as a serious problem as this indicator may refer to all practices and other information and trainings relevant to solid waste management. As perceived by the residents, the moderate extent of implementation of training on reduce, re-use and recycle points out only to that specific training and does not include all other practices.

Another inconsistency in the perception of both the residents and the barangay officials is the problem with regard to “no provision of public garbage bins” in which the barangay officials perceived it as a moderately serious problem while the residents perceived it as a serious problem. However, there is inconsistency in the results shown in Table 2. Indicator “provision of communal garbage bins especially to areas which are not accessible by the garbage truck” was perceived by the residents as highly

implemented while it was perceived by the barangay officials as moderately implemented. The inconsistency of the perceptions could be because the problem of “no provision of public garbage bins” may refer to the giving of bins to all the residents in the barangay. Besides, the provision of communal garbage bins as shown in Table 2 clearly specifies to areas where entry of garbage truck is impossible. Thus, it does not equate to provision of the public garbage bins.

Community involvement is also important in addressing solid waste challenges. Since the problem comes from the community, the community is the ultimate waste generators. Therefore, its active participation and involvement especially in coming up with a solution is very important. The lack of attendance to meetings, lack of engagement in programs, and negative attitudes are just among the manifestations of lack of community involvement. One of the common reasons for the lack of community participation in solid waste management activities is busy schedules (Almazan et al., 2016).

It is likely that community participation offers benefits such as building local capacities and capabilities. This means that community participation may for instance increase awareness of knowledge and capacities that could improve the ability to negotiate as equals with authorities and other stakeholders in order to promote common objectives, and increase responsiveness to conflicts within the community. Aside from that, involvement in decision-making can ensure that the different needs and problems of the community are integrated into the project’s objectives. This would also help empower the community, affording people the opportunity to devise and initiate strategies to improve their situation (Subash, n.d.).

On the part of the residents, all indicators enumerated as the challenges encountered in the barangay were perceived by the residents as serious. This means that the residents somehow felt and experienced those challenges in their respective communities. They find that those challenges enumerated are present and in need of solution. For example, the City Environment and Natural Resources Office is amenable that the lack of garbage trucks is true and existent. Likewise, Hon. Dionie Amores claimed that community involvement and lack of funds and technical capability readiness were also some of the constraints affecting solid waste management practices of every barangay in Dumaguete City.

The difference in perception of the challenges encountered in the barangay is due to the difference in involvement and responsibility in solving the challenges encountered. Barangay officials would most likely find the challenges as moderately serious since they are the implementers and enforcers of the solid waste management practices. On the other hand, the residents who are the recipient of the services of the barangay would most likely think and observe the challenges as serious as it may somehow influence their satisfaction level.

Difference in perceptions are due to a number of factors which creates perceptual filters or cultural frames that influence our responses to situation, such as:

culture, race, and ethnicity; gender and sexuality ; and knowledge and previous experiences (University of Wisconsin-Madison, Office of the Human Resource Development).

Relatively, study entitled “The Perception of Households About Solid Waste Management in Malaysia”, found out that there is a strong positive relationship between age and waste reduction behaviors. And the majority of the respondents agreed that their lifestyle affected waste minimization. Almost half of the respondents indicated that they lacked knowledge to practise waste sorting. Aside from that, age and education were positively correlated to reuse and recycling behaviors. Hence, a holistic waste management education is vital for Malaysia to build an efficient waste management system.(Choon, et al, 2017).

In Cebu City, there were barriers in the implementation of solid waste management. The city is particularly experiencing on-going funding difficulties related to hiring of waste management staff, and procurement of the necessary SWM facilities, technology and equipment. In addition, bureaucratic obstacles hindered effective policy coordination and implementation because of non- continuous operation that is caused by the shifting political priorities of subsequent administrations. In addition, a number of barangay officials have limited understanding of the implementation procedures of RA 9003 (Gamaralalage et al., 2017).

As far as waste collection is concerned, the city introduced separate waste collection systems to prevent mixed waste generation at source. However, it has been proven difficult to implement due to financial constraints and weak levels of public awareness and compliance (Gamaralalage et al., 2017).

Conclusions

The data reveals that the solid waste management practices in the barangay are perceived positively by both barangay officials and residents, though with varying degrees of effectiveness and challenge. The creation of the Barangay Solid Waste Management Committee is highly regarded by both groups, with barangay officials rating it at 4.00 and residents at 3.61, indicating strong institutional support. The "No Segregation, No Collection" policy also receives high ratings, with officials at 3.47 and residents at 3.41, demonstrating a broad compliance with segregation mandates. Composting of biodegradable waste and the establishment of a Material Recovery Facility are seen as moderately high, with officials and residents rating these aspects in the low to mid-3 range, showing some room for improvement. The promotion of the Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle (3R) initiative is also moderately high, suggesting ongoing but not fully effective efforts in waste reduction strategies. The collection and disposal of solid waste are well-rated, with officials at 3.73 and residents at 3.51, indicating general satisfaction with these services. However, challenges are perceived more severely by residents (3.60) compared to barangay officials (3.29), highlighting a potential disconnect in understanding or communication about the difficulties faced in managing solid waste. Overall, while there is a strong foundation and positive reception of waste

management practices, there is a need for better communication and perhaps more robust strategies to address the challenges perceived by the community.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, the researcher proposed the need to revisit the national policy on Ecological Solid Waste Management Act to where ordinances were based from in order to determine areas for improvement for an effective and strong top-to-bottom enforcement and implementation. Meanwhile, on the part of the LGU of Dumaguete, the city must allocate budget for the equipment, facilities and capability building of its personnel in the CENRO and barangay officials relative to the community that can address the solid waste management challenges. On the other hand, the National Government should assist and help the Local Government especially in the barangay level in the implementation of RA 9003 in terms of technical know-how, strong enforcement from the top down to the bottom of the hierarchy, clear alignment and doable direction of the program.

Since there is decentralization at the barangay level in the implementation of RA 9003, barangays should come-up with a PESTLE analysis that would help identify possible constraints, challenges, challenges and opportunities in the implementation of an effective solid waste management. Through that, they could come-up with appropriate solutions or programs.

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